

PADDY SEEDS SELLING AND DISTRIBUTION WEBSITE

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Abstract. Implementing a motivation system for paddy seed selling and distribution in Myanmar is crucial for bolstering the nation's agricultural sector and enhancing rice production. Traditional supply chains often suffer from inefficiencies, delays, and high costs, leading to reduced profitability and customer satisfaction. This system aims to enhance efficiency and reduce waste, ensuring timely delivery of high-quality paddy. Moreover, supporting local communities and collaborating with farmers fosters strong relationships and contributes to regional development. So, the paddy selling and distribution system aims to create a more efficient, sustainable, and profitable business model that benefits all stakeholders, including farmers, distributors, consumers, and the environment.

Keyword: Paddy Sale & Distribution, Online, HTML, CSS, PHP, XMAPP

INTRODUCTION

This project focuses on the development of a dedicated website for the selling and distribution of paddy seeds, aiming to modernize and improve access to high-quality seeds for farmers. The platform serves as a digital marketplace where seed producers and distributors can reach a wider audience, and farmers can easily browse, compare, and purchase paddy seeds suited to their specific agricultural needs. The website incorporates key features such as detailed seed information, secure online transactions, and efficient delivery logistics to streamline the seed acquisition process. By utilizing modern web technologies, the platform is designed to enhance user experience, reduce distribution bottlenecks, and provide a reliable source of premium seed varieties.

PROBLEM

This website is a website to help farmers easily buy and receive quality paddy seeds. Farmers face problems like getting fake seeds, not having enough information, and dealing with slow delivery. The new website will let farmers quickly order certified seeds, get information on different types of seeds, and use secure payment methods. The site will also offer advice to help farmers choose the right seeds for their land. By solving these issues, the website aims to boost rice farming in Myanmar, help farmers earn more money, and support the country's agricultural growth.

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APPROACH

The front-end of the paddy seeds website will be designed to make it easy for farmers in Myanmar to buy seeds and get the information they need. The site will be user-friendly, work well on the Internet, and be available in Burmese language. It will have clear menus, a simple layout, and features that make it accessible to everyone. We use some programming languages, such as HTML, CSS, Bootstrap for building the site and make sure it loads quickly and smoothly. We'll also test everything thoroughly to ensure it works well and meets farmers' needs. After launching the site, we'll provide support and updates to keep improving it.

A system flow diagram is a visual representation of the flow of data or processes within a system. It illustrates how different components of a system interact and how information moves between them. These diagrams are particularly useful for understanding complex systems, designing new systems, or analyzing and improving existing ones.

This system consists of two roles. There are Administrator and User. Users can view home page when the system start. After, users can view the paddy seeds age group and can also view the types of paddy seeds. User can order and buy that paddy seeds varieties. And then, user can send the feedback message for their problems and suggestions.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Admin must be login first. When admin successfully login, admin can view home page. And then, admin can view the paddy seeds age group and can manage insertion, deletion, and update for that paddy seeds age group. And then, admin can view types of paddy seed page. Similarly, admin can also manage that the types of paddy seeds. Admin can read the suggestion from users. Moreover, admin can view order status. And then, admin can see the person who distribute rice further. Those people can also be inserted, deletion, and update.

Figure 2: Database Design

An Entity Relationship Diagram uses data modeling techniques that can help define business processes and serve as the foundation for a relational database. An ERD attribute can be denoted as a primary key, which identifies a unique attribute, or a foreign key, which can be assigned to multiple attributes [2]. A cardinality notation can then define the attributes of the relationship between the entities. In the database, there are six data tables for administrator and five data tables for the user. The tables are users, feedback, type of paddy

seeds. The figure 2 shows database design for all the data tables and their relationship of the database.

RESULTS

The study found several key areas where improvements in the paddy seed selling and distribution system could benefit Myanmar's agriculture. Enhancing quality control and certification can ensure that farmers receive high-quality seeds, leading to better crop yields and higher incomes. Improving the distribution network and infrastructure will make it easier for small farmers to access quality seeds, especially in remote areas. Strengthening the regulatory framework and providing more support through agricultural extension services can help stabilize seed availability and prices. These positive changes can boost agricultural productivity, support farmers' livelihoods, and contribute to food security and rural development in Myanmar.

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

Overall, the paddy seeds website has greatly improved access for farmers in Myanmar. The site is available in Burmese languages, and has features that help people. Farmers can find information quickly thanks to clear menus and an efficient search tool. The website loads fast and works smoothly. Positive feedback from farmers shows that they are satisfied with the website, and ongoing updates ensure that it continues to meet their needs. So, the site has become an important tool for farmers, helping them improve their farming practices and earn more money.

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